

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

SIMPLE SENTENCE, ITS ACTANTS AND VARIABILITY

Sardarova I.

PH.D., associate professor

Azerbaijan University of Languages

Baku/Azerbaijan

Orcid: 0009-0003-8302-1498

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14770195>

Abstract

The article studies the variability of simple short sentences. Regardless of the specific language, the sentence is presented as the main means of communication. The author writes that sentences of different structures and different lengths are used in the communication process, depending on the volume of the thought used.

The article states that sentences in English are divided into two main groups according to their structure: 1) simple sentence; 2) complex sentence.

Introduction

The grammatical form of the sentence is not the same as its formal syntactic structure. The grammatical form of the sentence consists of two inseparable aspects: formal-syntactic on the one hand, and intonation on the other. "The grammatical form of a sentence is its scheme, in other words, it is the rule of general expression of thought through language. In the grammatical form of the sentence, its syntactic organization appears as the basis of the sentence - that is, its eternal property. At the same time, intonation creates countless options. This can be explained by the fact that, unlike the syntactic form, which manifests itself in the internal relationship between words and sentences in separate parts of the sentence, its intonation form has the ability to express external relations in a contextual flow along with internal relations" [Dressler 1978, p.4].

In this context, the problem arises from the conflict between the objective factor and the subjective factor. Although the intonation formation is mainly related to the objective factor, it can also be shown as a subjective evaluation, so that the subjective evaluation can be given in the framework that the possible aspects of the given syntactic structure are advanced [Zvegintsev 2007, p.4].

In modern linguistics, research on intonation reflects its participation in expressing the content of speech and in forming the content of communication by interacting with lexical-grammatical means. When we talk about the syntactic function of intonation, we should not only mean the composition of the communicative type of the sentence, turning it into a whole, but also the syntagmatic articulation of intonation, which is associated with the meaning and grammatical structure. According to L.R. Zinder, prosody performs two functions: emotional and the communicative function that opposes it. In the second sense, he understands everything that connects prosody with the meaning and syntactic structure of the sentence [Zinder 1976, p. 268].

Then he notes the main meanings of the communicative aspect of intonation:

- 1) It is a means of dividing speech into sentences;
- 2) It participates in determining the communicative types of the sentence;

- 3) It participates in the actual articulation of the sentence and divides it into syntagms, etc. [Zinder 1976, p. 271].

Intonation, which is the template of a sentence, is not only limited to giving a communicative unit a certain form, but also divides the thought into small units of meaning - syntagms, in order to make it understandable. However, intonation cannot act independently in isolation from the syntactic and lexical material. Its sphere of action is organically connected with the syntactic activity of the sentence. However, as noted, intonation is a phonological tool that carries a certain function in the language, actualizing the sentence for the expression of the thought.

Simple sentences and their relationship with relatively small speech units are also important conditions. Compared to other people, it is called a syntagm in our language. This term was introduced to linguistics for the first time by the Russian scientist, Academician L.V. Sherba. He considered the syntagm "the main syntactic unit in the speech process [Shcherba 1963, p.86].

"There is a fundamental difference between a sentence and a syntagm. A sentence is composed of one or several groups of syntagms expressing a finished thought, which are normally accompanied by a lowering of the tone of voice" [Shcherba 1963, p.86].

"If the syntactic structure of a sentence is associated in the form of an elaborate form during the speech, the syntagm is considered to be an occasional event and this fact is understood only as an independent speech element. This speech element is mainly obtained by the intonation structure, the moment of intonation, which unites the syntagm, etc." [Shcherba 1974, p.5].

A simple sentence is usually studied as a unit expressing one thought. The article also touches on the division of simple sentences into two subgroups. They are: 1) Simple short sentences; 2) simple extended sentences. The article provides information about the fact that sentences consisting only of main members are simple short sentences [Musayev 1997, p. 101].

From the first moments when people began to understand themselves, they began to be interested in the material and spiritual world surrounding them, in the wonderful secrets of this world, and not only did they

begin to study it, but they also became seriously interested in language, thinking about its origin, essence, and the role it plays in society, studying it, and trying to uncover its mysterious secrets. In those times, there was neither such a science, which we know today as linguistics, about which we make various, sometimes mysterious, opinions, nor linguists who studied it; in ancient times, the science of philosophy, which stood above all sciences, or more precisely, the founders of this science, philosophers, were engaged in various problems of language. At that time, language was one of the main problems that interested philosophers, made them think, and caused constant disputes among them.

In the early days, philosophers understood only individual words under the concept of language. They thought about the question of how the various words in the language were formed, whether there was a connection between words and the things and actions they expressed, and they first tried to solve this problem. This problem caused serious controversy among philosophers.

The names of two Greek scientists are most often mentioned in this field. One of them was Democritus, known in the history of philosophy as a materialist philosopher, and the other was Heraclitus, who claimed that everything in nature originated from fire and that fire was the primary substance in nature.

According to Heraclitus and his followers, there is a natural connection between words and what they express. According to Democritus and his followers, there is no connection between words and what they express; the meanings inherent in words have arisen simply as a result of the agreement between people.

Without opening a wide polemic in this area, we would like to say that here it is necessary to agree with Heraclitus's opinion. Because nothing in language is accidental, it is a law. Most likely, all the words existing in languages have arisen in a natural connection with what they express. When people created a word, they either likened it to the thing it expresses, or associated it with the time of occurrence of an event or state, or connected it with the place where the event occurred. Sometimes, words were created taking into account people's professions (for example, blacksmith, coal miner, oilman, driver, captain, butler, etc.), etc. [Musaev 1997, p.354].

Thus, the words used in the language arose in connection with the meaning they expressed and served as a means of communication between people.

It is impossible to imagine the emergence of words in each language in any other way. In fact, the emergence of language was formed by the emergence of words used in this language. That is why in ancient times, when people spoke of language, they first of all understood the word, and that is why the word and its emergence emerged as the first historical-philosophical problem of the science of language. Even today, such a problem makes philosophers and linguists think, and they deal with this problem from time to time [Brown et al 1983, p.26].

As for Democritus's hypothesis about the origin of words, that people created words based on the agreement they reached among themselves, it is absolutely impossible to believe in this. Because in the history of the development of language, even today, no word is created on the basis of the agreement of people in any language, this is absolutely impossible. Even terms that have a basic meaning in a language are not created in this way, that is, by the agreement of someone. In connection with the development of science and technology, literature and culture, and economy, a term is created by someone, and then it enters the use of all mankind. Thus, philosophers who equated words with language began to understand over time that language does not consist only of words, but as a means of communication, language cannot do without individual words. After that, linguists, in addition to studying individual words, began to identify another linguistic unit existing in the language - word combinations and study their inherent characteristics. After some time, linguists realized that neither individual words nor word combinations formed on their basis constitute a language as a means of communication [Gazdar 1979, p.101].

They realized that in order for language to be used as a means of communication between people, there must be another unit - the sentence. Because the main condition for communication, communicability, is possible only through the sentence and allows language to function as a means of communication. Thus, the language unit that we use today as a sentence and try to study its specific features has become the object of study of grammar (syntax).

In modern times, the science of linguistics has gone a little further and discovered the existence of another language unit that is important for communication - the text.

Thus, the development direction of the study of the grammatical structure of language can be shown approximately as follows:

A sentence is used in the process of communication and serves its creation. Communication is a multifaceted and complex process. In order to create communication, people have to express ideas with different purposes; they either provide information about this or that fact, or ask about it, or encourage the interlocutor to do something, or simply express their feelings and emotions in response to the influence they receive from the world around them. On the other hand, sentences have different lengths and different contents, depending on the idea they have to express [Bloomfield 1933, p.65].

Sentences used in the process of communication vary in terms of the purpose of expressing the idea and also in terms of their grammatical structure. Accordingly, sentences are usually classified and divided into types according to their purpose in communication and the structure they have.

Variability characterizes the general property of the language system as being realized in speech in the form of many variants. A variant is a specific realization of a linguistic unit, while variability is understood as the process of using variants and manifests itself at

all levels of the language. The concept of variability applies both to the language as a whole and to its various forms - oral and written, codified and dialect, territorial and social. This gives grounds to say that the manifestation in the form of variability and variants has a universal character [Lyons 1968, p.56].

The problem of variation has been explained in different ways in many languages at different times and is still being explained from different points of view not only in the linguistics of different peoples, but also in any national linguistics, and even in the works of specialists of the same language, and different representatives of the same linguistics. It is known that the concepts of "invariant" and "variant" entered linguistics from phonology.

When we talk about the components of the universal language in linguistics, we mean its two branches: 1) literary speech, or literary language; 2) non-literary speech, or colloquial language). This division is conditional as these branches of the universal spoken language do not operate in isolation from each other, but are in parallel and dynamic development.

The differentiation of language variability, its formation on the basis of certain norms, is for the purpose of ensuring the semantic disclosure of thought at the necessary level. In this regard, the phenomenon of variability in any language manifests itself in various forms. Therefore, in the semantic meaning and disclosure of thought, phonemes, sounds, stress, conjunctions and adverbs, complex sentences, mixed-type sentences, in short, certain language components, as well as the specific role of invariance and variation, have an important function. Recently, a number of studies have been conducted in the world, including Azerbaijani linguistics, on the problem of variability.

References:

1. Abdullayev, K.M. Theoretical problems of the syntax of the Azerbaijani language. Baku: Maarif, 1998, 284 p.
2. Brown, G. And Yule G. Discourse Analysis. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1983, 290 p.
3. Bloomfield, L. Language. New York, 1933, 277 p.
4. Chomsky, N. Aspects of the Theory of Syntax. Cambridge, Mass.: M.I.T.Press, 1965, 278 p.
5. Dressler, V. Text syntax // New in foreign linguistics. Issue VIII. Moscow, 1978, pp. 111-137.
6. Gazdar, C. Pragmatics. New York: Academic Press. United States of America, 1979, 250 p.
7. Lyons, J. Introduction to Theoretical Linguistics. Cambridge University Press. Great Britain, 1968, 380 p.
8. Lyons, J. Semantics. Cambridge University Press. Great Britain, 1977, 280 p.
9. Musayev, O.I. English grammar. Baku, Qismet, 1997, 609 p.
10. Yunusov, D.N. Constancy and variability in complex syntactic units. Baku: Mutarcim, 2008, 164 p.
11. Shcherba, L.V. Phonetics of the French language. Moscow: Higher School, 1963, 380 p.
12. Shcherba, L.V. Language system and speech activity. Leningrad: Nauka, 1974, 432 p.
13. Veysalli, F.Y. Selected Works. Baku: Mutarcim, 2008, 522 p.
14. Zvegintsev, V.A. The sentence and its relation to language and speech. Moscow: Moscow University Press, 2007, 308 p.
15. Zinder, L.R. General phonetics. Moscow: Vysshaya shkola, 1979, 312 p.